

ARTISTIC MANIFESTATION OF THE ISSUES OF HUMANISM IN THE NOVEL "JANE EYRE" BY CHARLOTTE BRONTË

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Abstract

The novel *Jane Eyre* is still widely read in modern society, and there are many controversial opinions surrounding the novel. Because Brontë draws the reader into the story and brings a modern aspect to the center of attention in the novel. Jane cleverly does this by appealing to the reader, "Reader, I married her..." to draw attention back to herself. In doing so, the reader is instantly pulled back every time they engage with the novel, therefore making it a more immediate action and happening in that very moment. This helps to capture the true essence of the novel and illuminates all the major important issues. All of the issues Brontë discusses are relevant to modern audiences and this has helped keep *Jane Eyre* a classic. Charlotte Brontë challenges the idea that men are emotionally, socially, and intellectually superior to women: "We women and men are equal as men are equal when we pass from the grave and stand at the feet of God!" (1)

The 19th century was a time of oppression for women. The patriarchal system that dominated the Victorian period in English history was one that Charlotte Brontë wrote and defined in her novel *Jane Eyre*. Brontë denounces the persecution women suffered at the hands of a society that believed men were emotionally, socially, and intellectually superior to Victorian women.

Keywords: Charlotte Brontë, *Jane Eyre*, women's liberation, Victorian Literature.

The belief that men were intellectually superior to women tainted the Victorian era. During that period, it caused women to be deprived of education based on their gender. *Jane Eyre* appears to be more intellectually advanced than her male counterparts despite being educated at a school with low standards such as Lowood. A school where not only the food, but also the facilities are "disgusting". She can confidently speak decisively and freely and on an equal footing even with men she does not consider superior to her. It is clear that Brontë strongly believes that women are equal to men in this regard. The fact that Jane was able to create "as beautiful a picture of Mrs. Reed as any painter could" (1) also indicated Brontë's support for the idea that women were as intellectually capable as men. Jane's skill in her paintings has led to criticism from some of the men who see her handiwork: "It seems to me that a hand has painted these pictures: is that your hand?" (3) By Jane's action against the stagnation of society, Brontë's disdain for society's limitations is demonstrated.

The Victorian era was a time when women's emotions were suppressed. It expressed the belief that men are emotionally superior to women. Brontë expressed her opposition to this idea by introducing the "passion picture" of *Jane Eyre*. This emotion and passion would not have been tolerated by others in Victorian society. Jane often "attempted some things like passion" in her youth. This was evident from his confrontation with John Reed; "You are like a murderer - you drag to be a slave." (2) In Victorian society, not only women, even young girls, did not usually display their anger. Brontë believed that the expression of women's emotions was crucial.

Arguing that women are not inferior to men, Brontë explains the reason for this idea by the fact that a woman has to climb up the social ladder or that she is "worthy of work and competent to do it". Love was a

factor that many people denied. Brontë condemned this denial. Calvinism, a patriarchal religious system, taught its members that men were superior to women in many ways, including morals. The most "moral" people in Victorian society seemed to be Brocklehurst-type figures who were actually hypocrites. They were seen as pious and the chosen few to enter the gates of Heaven. Brontë portrays Brocklehurst as a shallow person and in the end, he loses his job because of his lack of humanity.

Victorian society had discriminating classes, differences between men and women. Thus, lines of inequality arise between both sexes. Brontë believed that women were equal to men in terms of intellect, emotions, morals, and also in relationships. Although these ideas originated in the mid-1800s, a modern reader may hold these beliefs. *Jane Eyre* challenged Victorian beliefs with phrases like "Traditionality is not morality. Loyalty to oneself is not a religion."

"You are dependent, my mother says that you have no money, your father left you alone. You should beg and not live here with the lords' children like us, eat our food, and dress at our mother's expense. Now I'm going to teach you to sort through my bookshelves, because they're mine, I own the whole house, or I will in a few years." (6). This quote expresses John's power and authority over Jane. Because he unexpectedly reveals that he is socially dependent on John and uses this fact to exclude him. Jane, on the other hand, rejects the idea of being born an orphan and uses it as a weapon to be treated as an equal. The Lowood Institute is a disciplined environment that exists to prevent any non-conformity of young women. However, Jane sees it as a chance for a fresh start, somewhere where she won't be judged on her financial worth. Unfortunately, this is not the case in the beginning, as Jane is oppressed by Mr. Brocklehurst, a vile and scheming man who profits from the misery of orphaned children. Oppression is a

central theme of the novel and is closely related to the class structure, as other characters in the novel use it to victimize Jane and exert power over her.

When Mr. Brocklehurst humiliates Jane in front of the whole school, Brontë expresses the unfair dominance of the upper classes. He uses contrasting language to describe Mrs. Reed in relation to Jane to emphasize the social ideology created by the class system. Mr. Brocklehurst uses positive connotations to describe Mrs. Reed as "charitable, compassionate" simply because she is upper class, while portraying the lower-class Jane as "terrible, evil". Jane must then fight against any negativity associated with her class and force people to accept her for who she is. Because Lowood provided the same education, knowledge, and behavior associated with aristocrats, it helped him increase social class mobility. This highlights the importance of social boundaries established in society and how insignificant they are as they do not reflect a person's ability or potential. Brontë's portrayal of governesses is one of the most important positions when exploring the topic of social class.

In nineteenth-century Britain, life was governed by social class and hierarchy, and people rarely moved from one class to another. As an orphan, Jane had received a high standard of education to become a governess at the time, she does not have a definite social status and therefore falls between classes. She has an ambiguous social position as she lives with and converses with people from all walks of life, from working-class servants to upper-class aristocrats. Jane therefore causes extreme tension because she has upper-class sophistication but a lower-class background. Governesses of this era were expected to adhere to the high standards of aristocratic 'culture', but were often treated very badly by their employers.

Brontë created the Jane Eyre character with social mobility to help develop a wider community in the novel, therefore allowing the story to be more flexible. Brontë's protest is against the limitations of the social class system in England, and she creates problematic situations and events in the novel to highlight the social pressures practiced during this time. She cleverly transcends the boundaries created for both women and the lower classes, creating a stereotypically anti-normative character. However, Jane does not break every social rule as she refuses to marry Mr. Rochester when she learns the truth about his marriage. Although her marriage to Bertha is indeed loveless, Jane is determined not to subject herself to such moral depravity, and is proud to admit that even in the face of love, such an act would cast her out of society. This devotion to her personal morality underscores Jane's self-reinforcement that she will not succumb to the pressures of marriage for social status and wealth.

Jane begins to question her own class and self-worth when she meets her complete opposite, Blanche Ingram. Blanche is everything that Jane is not, rich and beautiful. Jane soon realizes the harsh truth and becomes acutely aware of the reality that her social class is holding her back from what she truly wants in life, Mr. Rochester. "A greater fool than Jane Eyre never

walked the earth, a more terrible fool never fell for sweet lies and swallowed poison like honey."(6)

In this self-awareness, Jane Eyre expresses regret and hatred by referring to herself in the third person. Jane mocks herself by using words like "Silly, foolish" because she believes she might ever be good enough for Mr. Rochester. How could a woman of low class and no status deserve to have a relationship with a man of such high stature and worth? Acting as an outside observer in her own actions, Jane is very harsh and critical of herself. Jane is a woman who always considers herself a valuable, admirable member of society and is proud of who she is. But after this episode, Jane's self-confidence is dramatically shaken, and she now judges herself and the other characters in terms of class and status.

After escaping from Thornfield Hall, Jane embarks on a homeless, free, penniless and hungry journey to find freedom and purity in her life. In a strange town, far from where she has adapted, Jane faces real poverty. She now has no class, no property, no value, no status. The only useful thing Jane can do is her willingness to work.

"I remembered that strangers who come to a place where they don't have any friends and want to get a job, sometimes turn to a clergyman for introductions and help. It is the duty of a cleric to help those who want to help themselves, at least with their advice".

Here, bereft of everything, Jane found confidence and courage in the trail of hope for a new beginning. She can promise to commit to herself and be grateful to anyone who lends a helping hand. However, Jane's fears are repeated when she is greeted at the door of her only hope by Hanna, the maid at the Marsh End residence. Hanna, a maid of not so high class herself, makes the same assumptions that Jane, who has suffered all her life, is a pointless orphan.

"To my horror, Hanna had a look of utter disbelief on her face. This was the climax. A strong pang of conscience, a real pang of despair, pierced my ears and roared. I cried in the most desperate agony. It's a pity that this isolation, this expulsion is because of my class!"(9)

In this statement, Jane confirms how worthless Hanna thinks she is. This overwhelming feeling of emotion at this point in the novel depicts Jane becoming tired and frustrated at being judged and ostracized because of her social class. Referring to the "climax" tells the reader that this is the height of despair and that Jane will soon overcome the problem. At Marsh End, Jane finds the independence and freedom she seeks, learns that she has living relatives, and discovers that she is rich. She has been freed from the strict social hierarchies imposed by the English class system, and now that Jane is rich, she has a sophisticated attitude and class status to match her education. When Jane shares her wealth with the Rivers family, it shows that Jane is not looking for wealth and fortune, but independence and freedom. Jane's inheritance is not a chance for material wealth, but rather gives her the right to live as an independent woman and ensure her acceptance in society as she is not dependent on anyone or anything. From

a young age, and throughout the novel, Jane seeks this rightful passage into the social class system.

Throughout the novel, several characters mention Jane's uncle John Eyre, indicating that he will leave Jane a significant inheritance. Although Jane believes their relationship is bad, Bessie mentions in chapter ten that John Eyre once came to see Reed, but Mrs. Reed lied about Jane's whereabouts. Bessie insists that John Eyre "looked very gentlemanly," contradicting Jane's belief that her relatives were poor. Mrs. Reed's lie also raises suspicions that she is hiding Jane from her caring relatives. Mrs. Reid later confirms these suspicions in her dying confession in chapter twenty-one, when she reveals that she wants to adopt Jane after John Eyre's successful business ventures in Portugal. These events characterize Mrs. Reed as spiteful and cruel. However, these moments also create hope, implying that Jane is not truly alone in the world. Outside Gateshead, a letter to the Rivers sisters informing them of their uncle John's death also shows Jane's legacy. The details of their uncles' lives fit very well with what the reader knows about Jane's uncle.

Many of the gruesome events at Thornfield Hall feature the revelation of Rochester's previous marriage to Bertha Mason. Rochester tries to absolve himself of guilt when he vaguely refers to his first marriage as a "capital mistake" in chapter twenty. This strange conversation, along with Mr. Mason's visit, warns the reader that Mr. Rochester is hiding something. Grace Poole accuses Bertha of instigating an anonymous attempt to burn Rochester as a monstrous entity. Jane notes how odd it is that Rochester hasn't fired Grace Poole, despite the fact that he's clearly a danger to everyone. These suspicions suggest that Grace Poole may not be the real culprit, even if she is a convenient prisoner. Bertha then wears the wedding veil and then destroys it, adding a sense of dread to Jane and Rochester's impending marriage. With thoughts of the past, Bertha wearing a wedding veil symbolizes that she is still Rochester's bride. Finally, a storm that destroys the chestnut tree shows that all is not well with Rochester's proposal to Jane. After Rochester vows that God is on his side, the storm rages on. By this time, the thunderbolt takes on the air of divine judgment and suggests that God disapproves of Rochester's actions.

Two events in particular herald the burning of Thornfield Hall. The first is when Bertha burns Rochester's bed. At this point in the novel, the fire emphasizes the feeling that all is not well in Thornfield. In retrospect, this attack reveals Bertha's penchant for burning things and her anger at Rochester. The second incident occurs a few days before her wedding to Rochester, when Jane dreams of Thornfield Hall in ruins while walking with a child in her arms. As this dream is one of Jane's two nightmares leading up to the wedding, it evokes a sense of anxiety surrounding her impending marriage. In retrospect, this dream heralds the end of Thornfield. The important point is that Jane said throughout the dream that she was trying to find a place for the child, but could not find a safe place among the rubble. Emphasizing that Jane and Rochester have a son in Fernand, the child in the dream symbolizes that Jane has no future at Thornfield.

Jane's decision to return to Mr. Rochester, which results in her settling in Fernand, stems from the maturity she has developed by increasing her knowledge of the society in which she lives. Before this he had entirely addressed himself to Mr. Rochester, and, notwithstanding his intellectual equality, was certainly not his social equal. Jane had nothing to give Rochester in a relationship with someone of such high status, but now that she is free and wealthy, she can confidently and freely stand by him despite society's judgments. On her return, Jane learns of the misfortune that has befallen Mr. Rochester, who has been blinded and physically injured in a terrible fire at Thornfield Hall. This is an important point in the novel because the gender roles have been reversed and Jane is now the stronger sex. The female role has become a dominant character, and the male role has become both dependent and powerless. In doing so, Brontë reflects Victorian gender relations as a critique of the repression of women by men. As a symbol of female independence and freedom, she almost "disempowers" Mr. Rochester's masculinity. Only now that Mr. Rochester has lost an important part of himself and Jane has now found freedom, they can be truly equal in their relationship and their characters are balanced. The thirty-seventh chapter of the novel concludes many unresolved dilemmas. It sheds light on themes of love, status, and identity, and restores friendship in Jane's life, freeing her from society's conventions and constraints.

Foreshadowing something throughout the work makes the novel even more mysterious. Brontë preemptively uses this technique to demonstrate that people who purport to care for Jane, or in Rochester's case, claim to love Jane, are not being honest with her, and to emphasize that Jane's place in the world is unstable. Only after the truths are revealed does Jane find safety and stability.

Conclusion

The novel "Jane Eyre" in the 19th century is a novel that has a special weight in bringing the socio-social characteristics of the era to literature, and it is a work that reflects the artistic manifestation of all these characteristics.

In the article, the reflection of the characteristics of that period in the novels, which are the leading literary genre of the Victorian era, the rebellion expressed in the novel against oppression and the historical and social reasons that caused this rebellion were investigated. As a result, in order to solve the problems of humanism of the Victorian era in the novel "Jane Eyre", problems such as class discrimination against people in society at that time, humiliation of personality, and insults are laid before the eyes, and social ugliness is revealed through a young girl who has no class. As a result of the research, it is known that it was the Victorian period of the 19th century that created fertile conditions for the creation and writing of the novel "Jane Eyre". In the article, the discrimination between people, which is observed throughout the novel, and the people belonging to the poor class are insulted at every opportunity, is mentioned as the main shortcoming of the society. It

is clear from the analysis of the characters and their actions that what will come to people's aid in a bad day is neither class stratification nor the existing state.

From the research, we clearly observe that the rapid development, industrialization, or material wealth occurring in society cannot become a savior of a person in difficult times. It is shown that the main wealth valuable for man in the world is human qualities and humanism.

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